

KOMITE ETIK PENELITIAN KESEHATAN

RUMAH SAKIT UMUM DAERAH dr. ZAINOEL ABIDIN

BANDA ACEH (23126)

Appendix 1: Explanation Sheet Before Approval

EXPLANATION BEFORE APPROVAL

I, Prof. Dr. Dr. Syahrul, Sp. S(K) NIM/NIP* 196202021989031001 Member dr. Nasrul Musadir., Sp.S, dr. Hidayaturrahmi, M.Sc., Sp.N Address Jl. Teuku Tanoh Abee, Kopelma Darussalam, Syiah Kuala University Banda Aceh Mobile Number 0811687196 Study Program/Institution* Neurology Faculty of Medicine Syiah Kuala University will conduct research entitled The Effectiveness of Using Mannitol on Clinical Outcomes in Severe Traumatic Brain Injury Patients

I will provide information to Mr/Mrs/Br(i) regarding this research and invite Mr/Mrs/Br(i) to become research subjects in this research.

If Mr/Mrs/Br(i) is willing to participate in this research then Mr/Ms/Br(i) can sign the Informed Consent form, but Mr/Ms/Br(i) can freely withdraw at any time. this research. If Mr/Mrs/Br(i) refuses to participate or withdraws from this research, that decision will not affect your relationship with me/the medical services provided*. If you do not understand each statement in this form, you can ask me.

Research objectives

Head injury is a disruption in brain function that occurs due to head impact, either directly or indirectly. In patients with severe head injuries, there is an increase in pressure in the brain so that the patient's consciousness can decrease. Mannitol administration aims to reduce pressure in the brain. Therefore, this study was conducted to assess the effectiveness of mannitol in patients with severe head injury (severe traumatic brain injury) by assessing the patient's condition (clinical outcome) after completing treatment at Dr. General Hospital. Zainoel Abidin Banda Aceh.

Participation in research

Patients who fall into the category of severe head injury (assessed based on level of consciousness) and receive mannitol therapy for ≤ 24 hours during treatment at Dr. General Hospital. Zainoel Abidin Banda Aceh with the condition that he agrees and has filled out the approval form first. If you do not agree, you cannot be included in this research.

Reasons for choosing Mr/Ms/Br(i)

Mr/Mrs/Br(i) was chosen to take part in this research because in this study the research samples were patients who fell into the category of severe head injury and had received mannitol therapy. The reason is to assess the patient's condition (clinical outcome) after completing treatment at Dr. Zainoel Abidin Banda Aceh.

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Research procedures

If Mr/Mrs/Br(i) is willing to take part in this research then Mr/Ms/Br(i) will be asked to sign a consent form, then Mr/Ms/Br(i) will be interviewed regarding the assessment of awareness, independence, physical activity, relationships, social and work ability after the treatment period based on the Glasgow Outcome at Discharge Scale (GODS) score. Score assessment was carried out on the last day of treatment.

Risks, side effects and management

This study has no risks and side effects because it only interviews patients with severe head injuries after treatment.

Benefits

The benefit obtained from this research is that you can find out changes in the patient's clinical condition after receiving mannitol therapy for severe head injuries.

Compensation

As a thank you from the researcher to Mr/Mrs/Br(i) who is willing to take part in this research, the researcher will provide a healthy drink (milk) as a sign of thanks.

Financing

All financing related to this research will be fully borne by the researcher

Confidentiality

Any information that Mr/Mrs/Br(i) provides while participating in this research will be treated confidentially so that it is impossible for other people to know. And all of your data will be stored on the researcher's personal laptop.

Obligations of research subjects

Mr/Mrs/Br(i) who has agreed to take part in this research has an obligation to answer questions honestly to ensure the validity of the research results.

The right to refuse and resign

Mr/Mrs/Br(i)'s participation in this research is voluntary and Mr/Mrs/Br(i) has the right to refuse participation in this research. Even though Mr/Mrs/Br(i) has agreed to participate, Mr/Mrs/Br(i) has the right to withdraw from this research. Mr/Mrs/Br(i) has the right to consider participation in this research after I have provided this explanation.

Additional Information

Mr/Mrs/Br(i) has the right to ask all questions related to this research. If you have further questions, you can contact me, Prof. Dr. Dr. Syahrul, Sp.S (K) on cellphone number 0811687196.

Best regards

(Prof. Dr. dr. Syahrul, Sp.S (K))

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Appendix 2 : Informed Consent

INFORMED CONSENT

After reading the form / hearing the explanation regarding the objectives, benefits, procedures and my rights related to this research, I sign below:

Name :
Age :
Sex :
Address :
Hand phone :

I hereby declare that, I am voluntarily and without coercion willing to be a respondent to participate in the research entitled "Effectiveness of Using Mannitol on Clinical Outcomes of Severe Traumatic Brain Injury Patients".

I know that this research upholds my rights as a research respondent and my participation as a subject in this research will be of great benefit to find out the relationship between Analyzing the effectiveness of the use of mannitol on the outcomes of clinical patients with severe traumatic brain injury at Dr. General Hospital. Zainoel Abidin Banda Aceh.

I believe that the information I provide will be kept confidential by the researcher and will only be used for research purposes. Thus, I have made this statement truly so that it can be used as necessary. Banda Aceh, 2023

Respondent

(Name and signature)

Research Questionnaire

GLASGLOW OUTCOME at DISCHARGE SCALE (GODS) v5

Name :
Date of Birth :
Room :

Date of Examination :
Examination Time :
Date of Injury :

Awareness	Score
<p>1a Is the patient conscious, i.e. able to perform simple commands, write, say a few words or communicate in other ways?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is the absence of response caused by sedation?* • Whether the person is diagnosed <i>with Vegative State</i>?* <p>*Note: Check with the nurses</p>	<p>1 – No 2 – Yes</p>
Independence in the Unit / Inpatient Room	
<p>2a Does he need nursing care and daily supervision for daily activities?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For a "No" answer, the person concerned must be able to take care of themselves for 24 hours even if they don't actually do it. • Self-reliance includes the ability to plan and perform the following activities: bathing, changing clean clothes, being able to prepare one's own meals, (e.g. in the OT (Occupational Therapy) kitchen or while at home), being able to deal well with visitors or other patients, and coping with minor problems, • The person concerned must be able to perform the above activities without the need for encouragement, supervision, or reminding, and must be trustworthy to be left alone overnight safely. • The person concerned must not endanger himself or others. 	<p>1 – No 2 – Yes</p>
<p>2b Does the person in question continue to need help or is someone nearby most of the time?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For a "No" answer, the person should be considered capable of taking care of themselves for up to 8 hours during the day if necessary, even if they don't have to. 	<p>1 – No (Upper SD) 2 – Yes (Lower SD)</p>
<p>2c Was home help needed before the injury?</p>	<p>1 – No 2 – Yes</p>
<p>2d Does the person in question seem dazed or confused?</p> <p>Has this been measured by the PTA (Post-Traumatic Amnesia) questionnaire? Y/N: If yes,</p> <p>The name of the questionnaire: and the score: [_____]</p> <p>Could it be that absent-mindedness and confusion are the effects of</p>	<p>1 – No (Upper SD) 2 – Yes (Lower SD)</p>

<p>administering sedatives? [Yes/No]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> If the person concerned is absent-minded or confused for some reason, then answer Yes to 2a 		SD)
<p>2e Is the behavior particularly disruptive or distressing to staff in the ward, visitors, other patients, or caregivers?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> No: May be antisocial, irritable, or passive/apathetic, but does not harm himself or others and does not require immediate or urgent attention. Yes: Very annoying or troublesome and may harm himself or others. Requires immediate or urgent staff intervention and special measures to minimise risks such as additional staffing or regular administration of sedatives. 		<p>1 – No (Upper SD)</p> <p>2 – Ya (Lower SD)</p>
Independence outside the Unit / Treatment Room		
<p>3a Is the person concerned able to shop without assistance?</p> <p>For example, in a hospital store, can the person in question plan what he wants to buy, use money properly, and successfully buy a number of items without help.</p>		<p>1 – No (Upper SD)</p> <p>2 – Yes</p>
<p>3b Was the person concerned able to shop unaided prior to the injury?</p>		<p>1 – No</p> <p>2 – Yes</p>
<p>4a Is the person concerned able to leave the unit/ward without assistance?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> They can walk, use a wheelchair, drive, or use public transportation to get around. Examples include visiting a hospital store independently and safely or traveling home, and successfully returning safely. Using a taxi is also sufficient if the person concerned can contact and instruct the driver. 		<p>1 – No (Upper SD)</p> <p>2 – Yes</p>
<p>4b Were they able to travel unaided before the injury?</p>		<p>1 – No</p> <p>2 – Yes</p>
Work		
<p>5a Are they considered to be able to work with their previous capacity?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> This relates to the ability to return to work within one week of discharge from the hospital, and to the advice they receive upon discharge from the hospital. If previously they worked, then their working capacity should be the same. If they have previously sought employment, the injury should not affect (negatively) their chances of employment or the level of work they are entitled to. If before the injury this patient was a student, then his capacity to learn should not be affected (negatively). 		<p>1 – No</p> <p>2 – Yes</p>

<p>5b Seberapa terbatas yang bersangkutan menurut Anda?</p> <p>a) Its working capacity is reduced b) Only able to work in workplaces that employ persons with disabilities separately or in non-competitive occupations, or are unable to work at all</p>		<p>1 = a (Upper MD)</p> <p>2 = b (Lower MD)</p>
<p>5c Was the person concerned working or looking for work before the injury (answer "Yes) or did neither" (answer "No")?</p>		<p>1 – No</p> <p>2 – Yes</p>
<p>Social activities and entertainment activities</p>		
<p>6a Are they able to participate in social activities and entertainment activities that are common in their neighborhood?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This includes social and appropriate interaction with other patients, therapists, staff and visitors. It also includes interest in other things such as television, radio, newspapers or other reading materials. If they do not participate in most entertainment or therapeutic activities due to loss of interest or motivation, then this can also be categorized as an inability or limitation. • The person concerned should engage in intellectual activity, and judgments about it should also be made. For example, checking them in a simple way such as asking what they are watching/have watched, read or listened to. 		<p>1 - No</p> <p>2 - Yes</p>
<p>6b To what extent are their social and entertainment abilities limited?</p> <p>a) Lightweight; spend half a day or more demonstrating social or intellectual interest, b) Moderate; spend less than half of the day demonstrating social or intellectual interest, c) Heavy; rarely, never even show social or intellectual interest.</p>		<p>1 = a (Lower GR)</p> <p>2 = b (Upper MD)</p> <p>3 = c (Lower MD)</p>
<p>6c Were they involved in social activities and entertainment activities that were routinely carried out outside the home before the injury?</p>		<p>1 - No</p> <p>2 - Yes</p>
<p>Social Relations</p>		
<p>7a Whether there is a psychological problem that results in impairment or difficulty in social relations with ward staff, families, visitors, other patients or carers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Post-head injury personality changes; His emotions are easily provoked, irritable, become aggressive, feel restless, become insensitive to others, rapidly changing moods, depression, and behave childishly. 		<p>1 - No</p> <p>2 – Yes</p>

<p>7b What is the impact of psychological problems?</p> <p>a) Problems that sometimes arise do not have a severe or prolonged impact.</p> <p>b) The problem is obvious, but still tolerable and does not occur every day.</p> <p>c) Causes of tension and resentment that are severe and occur continuously on a daily basis. It can cause or have caused damage in family relationships.</p>		<p>1 = a (Lower GR)</p> <p>2 = b (Upper MD)</p> <p>3 = c (Lower MD)</p>
<p>7c Was there a problem like this before the injury?</p>		<p>1 - No</p> <p>2 – Yes</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> If this kind of problem existed before the injury, and after the injury the problem becomes worse. <p>then answer "No" to 7c</p>		
<p>Return to normal life</p>		
<p>8a Are there currently other problems associated with injuries that could have a negative impact on daily life?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Other problems reported after a brain injury: headache, dizziness, fatigue, sensitivity to sound and light, being sluggish, forgetting frequently, and difficulty concentrating. 		<p>1 - No (Upper GR)</p> <p>2 - Yes (Lower GR)</p>
<p>8b Had a similar problem occurred before the injury?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> If this kind of problem existed before the injury, and after the injury the problem becomes worse and worse. <p>Then answer "No" to 8b</p>		<p>1 - No</p> <p>2 – Yes</p>
<p>What are the most important factors influencing such development? (put a tick)</p> <p>Impact of injury to the head ____</p> <p>Impact of illness or injury to other limbs ____</p> <p>A combination of the two ____</p>		
<p>Assessment: the overall assessment level is based on the lowest results of the category shown, which refers to the guidance of <i>the Glassglow Outcome at Discharge Scale</i> for more information on the administration of the assessment.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Death Unconsciousness Lower severe disability 		

4. Upper severe disability
5. Lower moderate disability
6. Upper moderate disability
7. Lower good recovery
8. Upper good recovery

*Patients with grades below 7 should not be released in an unsupervised community environment